

**A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON EMOTIONAL STABILITY, MOTIVATION,
AND POSITIVITY IN LIFE BETWEEN ACTIVITY PREFERENCES:
A BASIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A BALANCED YOUTH
LIFE PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 7

Pages: 897-905

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2401

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13832748

Manuscript Accepted: 08-23-2024

A Comparative Analysis on Emotional Stability, Motivation, and Positivity in Life Between Activity Preferences: A Basis in the Development of a Balanced Youth Life Program

Vanessa Mae J. Lagmay, * Jaemari Anne M. Padilla, Chloe Therese T. De Los Santos,
Kevin Brian DC. Inocentes, Arianne Rose V. Casinto, Selica Misty N. Navarrete

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of this comparative analysis study is to compare how students' motivation, emotional stability, and positivity in life are affected by indoor technology-driven activities compared to outdoor play activities. Furthermore, the researchers conducted their study at the St. Michael Institute of Bacoar, using quantitative methods to collect data. They surveyed one hundred and fifty senior high school students aged 18-20. The study used self-made questionnaires with sixty questions divided into three variables: emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life. The results show no significant difference between the levels of emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life based on the respondents' preferred activities. This study aims to promote outdoor play activities and a balanced lifestyle with indoor technology-driven activities. It will serve as a basis for suggesting activities that will boost motivation, emotional stability, and positivity in life.

Keywords: *emotional stability, motivation, positivity in life, outdoor activities and indoor technology activities*

Introduction

The argument that the difference between indoor technology-driven activities and outdoor play in modern society affects different components of human development—such as motivation, emotional stability, and general life positivity—has garnered considerable attention.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly altered how people engage with and experience the natural world, which may have far-reaching implications for individual and public health, as well as overall well-being (Jackson et al., 2021)

On the other hand, prolonged involvement in technology-driven indoor activities can cause elevated tension, anxiety, and social isolation, which can eventually undermine mental stability (Twenge & Campbell, 2020).

The research will explore how technology-driven indoor activities affect emotional well-being and motivation, emphasizing the risks of prolonged screen time and sedentary habits. It also suggests that insights into outdoor play preferences can benefit urban planning, community design, and psychology by examining lifestyle preferences psychological, societal, and cultural aspects. Additionally, enhancing outdoor play areas and offering diverse activities for various age groups can improve emotional stability and provide valuable insights into family dynamics and parenting practices.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the respondents' demographic profiles in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Activity Preferences
 - 1.2.1. Outdoor Play and
 - 1.2.2. Indoor Technology-driven Activities
2. What are their levels in terms of:
 - 2.1. Emotional Stability
 - 2.2. Motivation
 - 2.3. Positivity in Life
3. Is there a significant difference between the levels of emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life between respondents who prefer outdoor play activities and indoor technology-driven activities
4. Is there a significant difference between the emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life between males and females
5. Is there a relationship between the emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in the life
6. What activities can be suggested to encourage youth to participate in outdoor play activities and maintain a balanced lifestyle with indoor technology-driven activities?

Literature Review

Indoor Technology-Driven Activities

Iswidharmanjaya's theory, cited by Eka Setiawati et al 2019, suggests that using gadgets occasionally has a negative impact on users.

However, it also proposes that gadgets can have a positive effect. This positive effect is specifically observed when gadgets are used by children. It improves their language and mathematical skills, enhances visual acuity, and reduces stress. In early childhood, significant emotional developments include the ability to discuss personal and others' emotions and a growing comprehension of emotions. Children express various emotions, such as guilt, shame, pride, anger, and happiness. When children experience shame, they typically display body language indicating a desire to hide or conceal themselves. In contrast, feelings of guilt often lead to actions that aim to rectify mistakes or make amends.

A study by Bengtsson et al. (2021) suggests that online games are a form of entertainment and a significant social space for young people. This is especially true when we cannot be physically present, such as during the pandemic, which led to a surge in online activity. This highlights the effectiveness of online gaming as a platform that helps lessen feelings of social isolation, alleviates stress, and acts as a coping mechanism during trying times.

The study of Keskin et al. (2021) seeks to explore the correlation between the levels of digital game addiction among secondary and high school students and their motivation for engaging in physical activity during the pandemic. The research findings indicate a negative and moderately significant relationship between individual motives and the perceived futility sub-aspects of the physical activity motivation scale and digital game addiction. The study reveals an inverse relationship where higher motivation for physical activity corresponds to lower levels of digital game addiction.

According to a study by Piores et al. (2024), sedentary behavior is a global concern, with electronic device use among children contributing to inactivity. However, theoretical development on the relationship between gadget use and children's physical activity is limited. Insufficient physical activity among children, coupled with excessive screen time, is linked to negative health consequences, with less than 20% of adolescents adhering to recommended guidelines. The World Health Organization (2022) reports that less than 20% of adolescents worldwide follow the recommended physical activity guidelines, with excessive screen time contributing to sedentary behavior. Children are increasingly incorporating electronic devices into their daily routines, leading to a decrease in physical activity and a negative impact on the community. Children find happiness in interacting with friends using gadgets, emphasizing the importance of social connections during screen time, despite the assumption of solitude. The study found that physical activity is often seen as a last resort, with children turning to it when unwell or bored, and parents' attitudes reaffirming this behavior.

According to the study of Cagas et al. (2022), the prevalence of insufficient physical activity (PA) among young Filipinos is frighteningly high. Children's significant dependence on technology in the modern digital era impedes their capacity to engage in creative activities, physical exercise, and sensory development.

The study by Mungcal et al. (ca. 2021) delves into the escalating global obesity rates, particularly exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. The study investigates the perceived factors and barriers to physical exercise among at-risk and obese college students in the Philippines, highlighting the substantial health benefits of consistent physical activity.

The growing prevalence of electronic device usage among children has sparked discussions on its influence on emotional intelligence. Research suggests that moderate electronic device use can enhance children's emotional intelligence by improving social and communication abilities. However, excessive or unregulated screen time may lead to emotional challenges like anxiety, depression, and reduced awareness of their surroundings.

A study by Gagani et al. (2021) involving Senior High School students who engaged in flexible learning modality during the pandemic indicates that being emotionally stable equates to having good stress management. Since the pandemic added to the external factors of stress, everyone must be able to manage their stress efficiently. The findings indicate that individuals with high levels of emotional stability exhibit enhanced stress management capabilities, while those with lower levels of emotional stability tend to face more difficulties in managing stress effectively.

Outdoor Play Activities

The study by Rasheed (2021) highlights the key obstacles identified by students, including technical issues, limited face-to-face interaction, difficulties with time management and distractions, absence of a structured schedule, stress, the absence of traditional college experiences, restricted access to digital devices, and a lack of external learning resources. Physical Education (PE) instructors have noted that online classes for PE courses are ineffective in enhancing motor skill development and physical activity levels. This ineffectiveness to factors such as the absence of hands-on training, students' lack of motivation or interest in learning, and challenges in maintaining student engagement (Lobo, J. 2022)

According to Gutierrez et al. (2022), for certain scholars, games and play are considered essential and highly significant activities for children, serving as a foundation to prepare them for their future endeavors. Outdoor play activities impact cognitive and social development through physiological mechanisms. Games not only influence children's development but also play a crucial role in enhancing social and cultural aspects for youngsters. The results indicate that many children today prefer video games over traditional games, parents prioritize safety concerns that limit traditional outdoor play, and the prevalence of mobile phones with gaming apps has led to a decline in conventional game participation.

Physical and mental health challenges are becoming more prevalent among younger individuals, often originating from unhealthy

habits developed in childhood and carried into adolescence as lifestyle choices. Research highlights the benefits of outdoor activities for adolescents, promoting healthier behaviors, increased physical activity, and reduced screen time in rural settings.

In a study conducted by Firmante (2023), the objective was to investigate whether emotional stability predicts the effectiveness of students' general coping mechanisms. The findings showed that the students can cope well and have high emotional stability. However, although there is a correlation between emotional stability and coping abilities, scoring high on emotional stability does not necessarily imply that their coping skills are superior to others.

As per Apkinar, U. & Kandir A. (2022), educators highlight the importance of outdoor activities in fostering a child's comprehensive growth, impacting various areas. These benefits encompass enhancing emotional intelligence for effective social interactions, promoting physical, cognitive, and linguistic development, and nurturing self-help skills. Moreover, engaging in outdoor play is an enjoyable way for children to connect with nature. It has numerous benefits for a child's development, including health, cognition, and self-perception.

A study by Robinson (2020) found that 80% of parents needed to recognize the benefits of outdoor play in socio-emotional and cognitive development, and only one parent recognized its benefit in socializing. One parent noted that it is beneficial for building muscle strength and coordination and fostering self-esteem. The study suggests a gap between the existing literature knowledge and parents' awareness regarding other benefits of outdoor play.

According to the Pilot Study by Park, Lee, and Kim (2021), most people nowadays spend their leisure time in indoor environments. The findings of this pilot study indicate that engaging in horticultural activities serves as physical activity, heightens a positive response in brain activity, and changes emotional condition during a short tasking span. The researchers observed an increase in serotonin and tryptophan biosynthesis metabolisms, indicating increased feelings of happiness among the respondents.

Jackson et al. 's (2021) study underscores the significance of time spent outdoors and in natural environments in improving adolescents' resilience and ability to manage stressful experiences, such as the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. This underscores the necessity of providing and promoting outdoor recreation options for young people, especially during challenging periods.

Engaging in outdoor play is an enjoyable way for children to connect with nature. It has numerous benefits for a child's development, including health, cognition, and self-perception. When combined with spontaneous and unstructured play, children can cultivate their self-esteem through the diverse elements of unstructured play. To maintain focus, the play centers around an object that sparks the children's curiosity and enhances their imagination and creativity. This play also empowers children to make decisions and take risks (Runner, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

The study was conducted on Senior High School Students of St. Michael Institute of Bacoor, comprising 150 students aged 18 to 20. The researchers used the purposive sampling method, which, according to Campbell et al. (2020), ensures credibility with the data gathered and is aligned with the research objectives.

Respondents

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents*

	<i>Gender</i>		<i>Preference in Activities</i>		
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	
Male	66	49.3	Indoor	67	50
Female	67	50	Outdoor	67	50
Unspecified	1	0.7	Unspecified	0	0

Instrument

The researchers used self-made questionnaires that consisted of sixty (60) questions on a Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Uncertain, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). The questionnaires were divided into three (3) variables: emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life.

Procedure

The researchers created a questionnaire to measure the respondents' emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life. They then sought validation of the questionnaires from their thesis adviser and sent a letter of request to the St. Michael Institute of Bacoor administrators. The researchers utilized the purposive sampling method to select the respondents. Upon approval of the school administrators, the researchers provided the questionnaires administered to the respondents. Once the questionnaires are all filled out, the gathered data are sent to the statistician for analysis and interpretation. Lastly, the researchers reported the results to the St. Michael Institute of Bacoor and provided recommendations based on the research results.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of St. Dominic College of Asia based on the compliance with the minimum standards of the SDCA Research Guidelines. Respondents were deployed based on their willingness to participate in this study with informed consent.

Results and Discussion

The demographic data of the respondents: 1 representing (.7%) of the respondents were Unspecified, 66 representing (49.3%) of the respondents were Male, and 67 representing (50.0%) of the respondents were Female. It also shows the demographic data of the respondents' preferences in their type of activity: 67 representing (50.0%) outdoor play activity and 67 representing (50.0%) indoor technology-driven activity.

The respondents who preferred indoor technology-driven activities and those who preferred outdoor activities generally had the highest mean scores in the "positivity in life" factor. On the other hand, the "emotional stability" aspect received the lowest mean scores for both groups of respondents. Both male and female respondents generally have the highest mean scores in the "positivity in life" factor. On the other hand, the "emotional stability" aspect received the lowest mean scores for both respondents.

The test of significant differences in the assessment of motivation, emotional stability, and positivity in the life of the respondents who prefer indoor-technology-driven activities and outdoor activities in terms of gender First, the results yielded a p-value of 0.778 for emotional stability, indicating that it is not statistically significant. Second, the statistical analysis of the respondents' motivation levels when grouped according to their preference for playing activities. The result yielded a p-value of 0.513, indicating that it is not statistically significant. Lastly, when grouped according to their preference for playing activities, the statistical analysis of the respondents' different levels of positivity in life yielded a p-value of 0.086, indicating that it is not statistically significant.

The Level of Positivity in Life had a general assessment of 3.8321 (SD=1.1448) which was verbally interpreted as Agree, This can be concluded that the result indicates a generally positive level of motivation among the participants. The level of motivation and positivity in life of the respondents has a strong, positive correlation with a correlation coefficient of 0.739 and a p-value of 0.00, which is significant at a 5 percent level. On the other hand, the correlational analysis of positivity in life and emotional stability has a strong, positive correlation with a correlation coefficient of 0.691 and a p-value of 0.00, which is significant at a 5 percent level

Table 2. *The demographic profile and preference in activity of the respondents*

	Gender		Preference in Activities		
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Male	66	49.3	Indoor	67	50
Female	67	50	Outdoor	67	50
Unspecified	1	0.7	Unspecified	0	0

The study's findings were summarised according to the research problem statement, from the demographic profile to the statistical results. One hundred fifty senior high school students participated in this study; however, only 134 students qualified for the criteria. Among them, 67 were female students, and 66 were male students. Out of 134 respondents, 67 favored outdoor activities, while 67 students preferred indoor technology-driven activities, and 16 did not provide a preference.

Table 3. *The mean score of Emotional Stability, Motivation, and Positivity in Life (3 factors) for Indoor-Technology Driven Activities and Outdoor Activities*

Activities	Emotional Stability		Motivation		Positivity in Life	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Indoor	3.5913	.63837	3.7274	0.6232	3.7321	0.6575
Outdoor	3.6205	.65028	3.8003	.66237	3.9321	.68084
Total	3.6059	0.6443	3.7639	0.6428	3.8321	0.6692

The result shows that positivity in life among male respondents has the highest mean score of 3.7, while the emotional stability aspect of the respondents has the lowest mean score of 3.5. Conversely, among female respondents, the highest mean score is also for positivity in life, with 3.9, while the lowest is for emotional stability, with 3.6. This means that the positivity in life of females is slightly higher than that of males, similar to emotional stability.

Table 4. *The mean scores of Emotional Stability, Motivation, and Positivity in Life (3 factors) for Male and Female*

Activities	Emotional Stability		Motivation		Positivity in Life	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Indoor	3.5913	.63837	3.7274	0.6232	3.7321	0.6575
Outdoor	3.6205	.65028	3.8003	.66237	3.9321	.68084
Total	3.6059	0.6443	3.7639	0.6428	3.8321	0.6692

The study found no significant difference between the levels of emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life between respondents who prefer outdoor play activities and indoor technology-driven activities. The emotional stability levels have a probability value of 0.778, meaning that the preference for activities does not significantly impact the respondents' emotional stability. The motivation levels of the respondents have a probability value of 0.513, which means that their preference for activity does not significantly influence the respondents' motivation. The positivity in life levels of the respondents has a probability value of 0.086, which means that their preference for activity does not significantly influence the respondents' positivity in life.

Table 5. *The Difference between the Levels of Emotional Stability, Motivation, and Positivity in Life between Respondents Who Prefer Outdoor Play Activities and Indoor Technology-Driven Activities*

	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Emotional Stability	.778	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Motivation	.513	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Positivity in Life	.086	Not Significant	Accept Ho

The study's correlational analysis of the relationship between emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in the life of respondents who prefer outdoor play activities to those who prefer indoor-driven technologies showed that emotional stability and motivation, motivation and positivity in life, and positivity in life and emotional stability have a strong, positive correlation coefficient with each other. This means that people who engage in outdoor play activities are linked to having higher emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life compared to those who prefer indoor technology-driven activities.

Table 6. *The Difference in terms of Motivation, Emotional Stability, and Positivity in Life between Male and Female*

	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Motivation	0.327	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Emotional Stability	0.235	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Positivity in Life	0.156	Not Significant	Accept Ho

The respondents' motivation, emotional stability, and positivity in life assessment based on gender showed that females have higher mean scores than males in all three variables. In motivation, female respondents scored a mean score of 3.8 with a probability value of 0.327, higher than the 3.7 mean score of male respondents.

Table 7. *The Relationship between the Emotional Stability, Motivation, and Positivity in the Life of Respondents*

	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Motivation-Emotional Stability	0.785	0.00	Strong, Positive Correlation	Significant	Reject Ho
Emotional Stability to Positivity in Life	0.691	0.00	Strong, Positive Correlation	Significant	Reject Ho
Positivity in Life- Motivation	0.739	0.00	Strong, Positive Correlation	Significant	Reject Ho
Total	0.738333	0.00	Strong, Positive Correlation	Significant	Reject Ho

The analysis of emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life among respondents through multiple correlations revealed a highly robust and positive relationship. The correlation coefficient 0.802 with a significant p-value of 0.00 at the 5 percent level indicates a strong association between these three factors.

The result shows positivity in life among male respondents has the highest mean score of 3.7 while the emotional stability aspect of the respondents has the lowest mean score of 3.5 among male respondents. Conversely, among female respondents, the highest mean score is also for positivity in life, with 3.9 while the lowest mean score is for emotional stability, with 3.6. This means that positivity in life of female is slightly higher than male similar with emotional stability

The study found there is no significant difference between the levels of emotional stability between respondents who prefer outdoor play activities and indoor technology-driven activities, with probability value of 0.778 which is less than the level of significance of 0.05. This claim is supported by Jackson et al., (2021) study which indicates that participation in outdoor activities has the potential to strengthen teenage resistance to environmental stressors.

The study found there is no significant difference in motivation levels among participants based on their preferred playing activities, with probability value of 0.513 which is less than the level of significance of 0.05 meaning suggesting that their preferred style of play does not significantly influence motivation. Adolescents who engage with personal narratives on peer-to-peer support websites and receive emotional and informational support, enhancing their ability to handle difficult situations (Mariën, S., et al.)

The study shows that participants' life positivity levels based on their preferred playing activities did not show any statistically significant differences with probability values of 0.086 which were lesser than the level of significance of 0.05. A study by Slavinski, et.al (2021), discussed how there are several factors that influence the youths' life satisfaction ranging from academics, family, their environment, and financial status. He also highlighted that being physically active or participating in sports plays a significant role in improving one's well-being.

The participants' motivation assessment among respondents who favor indoor technology-driven activities and outdoor activities based on gender and male has a mean score of 3.7 and female respondents has 3.8 and a probability value of 0.327 which is lesser than the level of significance of 0.05; This means that female has higher motivation than men and it reveals no statistically significant difference in motivation levels between male and female participants. A study by Bećirović (2017) showed that female students display higher motivation across components: extrinsic motivation, personal goals, attitudes, and motivational strength than male students. He claimed that male and females are not equal in terms of motivation.

The participants' assessment in emotional stability levels between male and female respondents based on their preferred activities. Male participants had 3.5 while female participants had 3.6 with a probability value of 0.235 which were less than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, there is no significant difference in terms of motivation between male and female respondents. This claim is supported by the study of Sergi, et. al (2021), where the findings showed that gender has no role when it comes to emotional intelligence, anxiety, and depression.

The participants' assessment in life positivity levels between male and female respondents based on their preferred activities, whether indoor technology-driven or outdoor activities. Male has 3.7 positivity in life while female has 3.9 with a probability value is 0.156 which is less than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, there is no significant difference in terms of motivation between male and female respondents. The results of a study by Šnele, et.al (2020) showed that attributes related to femininity are predictors of a positive outlook in life. Therefore, women scored higher than men, though it is a small difference since the mentioned attributes are both present in women and men.

The analysis of emotional stability, motivation, and life positivity among respondents through multiple correlations revealed a highly robust and positive relationship. The correlation coefficient of 0.802 with a significant p-value of 0.00 at the 5 percent level indicates a strong association between these three factors. This is supported by Leong (2022)'s study, wherein they emphasize that educators must understand the concept of emotional stability, the factors that affect motivation, and to encourage positive emotions among learners. Emotions can easily sway the learner's motivation and therefore, hinder their performance and growth. However, maintaining a positive outlook can easily offset negative emotions among students. The study's small sample size of 150 respondents limits its reliability and resilience, making it challenging to draw firm conclusions or extend the findings to a larger setting. The lack of prior research on a subject can hinder the contextualization of findings within current knowledge, making it challenging to expand on hypotheses or recognize new findings. These limitations could have affected the findings by restricting the scope and generalizability of the study.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drafted:

There is no significant different between the level of the respondents' emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life based on their preference of activities.

There is no significant difference found between males and females in terms of the level of their emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life.

There is a strong positive relationship between emotional stability, motivation, and positivity in life.

References

- An, H. Y., Chen, W., Wang, C. W., Yang, H. F., Huang, W. T., & Fan, S. Y. (2020). The Relationships between Physical Activity and Life Satisfaction and Happiness among Young, Middle-Aged, and Older Adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(13), 4817. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134817>
- Akpınar, U. & Kandır, A. (2022). Investigation of preschool teachers' views on outdoor play activities. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, 12(2), 235–245. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.12.02.23>
- Barton, B. A., Adams, K. S., Browne, B. L., & Arrastia-Chisholm, M. C. (2021). The effects of social media usage on attention, motivation, and academic performance. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 22(1), 11-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787418782817>
- Bengtsson, T. T., Bom, L. H., & Fynbo, L. (2021). Playing Apart Together: Young people's online gaming during the COVID-19 lockdown. *Young*, 65–S80. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11033088211032018>
- Cagas, J. Y., Mallari, M. F. T., Torre, B. A., Kang, M. D. P., Palad, Y. Y., Guisihan, R. M., Aurellado, M. I., Sanchez-Pituk, C., Realin, J. G. P., Sabado, M. L. C., Ulanday, M. E. D., Baltasar, J. F., Maghanoy, M. L. A., Ramos, R. A. A., Santos, R. A. B., & Capió, C. M. (2022). Results from the Philippines' 2022 report card on physical activity for children and adolescents. *Journal of exercise science and fitness*, 20(4), 382–390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesf.2022.10.001>

- Chan, W.K., Leung K.I., Ho, C.Co., Wu, C.W., Lam, K.Y., Wong, N.L., Chan, C.Y.R., Leung K.M., & Tse, A.C.Y. (2021). Effectiveness of online teaching in physical education during COVID-19 school closures: a survey study of frontline physical education teachers in Hong Kong. Department of Health and Physical Education, The Education University of Hong Kong, 21, 1620-1628. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2021.04205>
- Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D., & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: complex or simple? Research case examples. *Journal of research in nursing : JRN*, 25(8), 652–661. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>
- Carstens, K.J, Mallon, J.M., Bataineh, M., & Al-Bataineh, A. (2021). Effects of Technology on Student Learning. *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, volume 20 Issue 1. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1290791>
- Dienlin, T. & Johannes, N. (2020). The impact of digital technology use on adolescent well-being^{SEP}. *Dialogues in clinical neuroscience*, 22(2), 135–142. <https://doi.org/10.31887/DCNS.2020.22.2/dienlin>
- Elisa, D., Permana, S., & Ericson, C. (2022). Analysis of Gadget Use (Online Game Addiction) and Emotional Intelligence on Student Learning Motivation in Pandeglang City Senior High School. *International Journal of Education, Information Technology, and Others*, 5(4), 134-138. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6983946>
- Firmante, M. C. M. (2023). Emotional Stability as Predictor of General Coping among Engineering Students. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, VII(VI), 1052–1057. <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2023.7688>
- Eka S., Elih S., Habib C. & A Dewi (2019). The Effect of Gadget on Children’s Social Capability. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1179, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1179/1/012113>
- Fletcher, R. (2021) An Exploration of the Barriers and An Exploration of the Barriers Motivators to Outdoor Active Play for Young People Aged 11-12: Why Don’t They Play Anymore? Masters Thesis, University of Huddersfield. Retrieved from <https://eprints.hud.ac.uk/id/eprint/35483/>
- Gagani, F., Carredo, B., Daan, E. A. ., Enriquez, J., Fernan, M. J. ., Manlunas, I., & Tayurang, E. J. (2021). Investigating students’ emotional stability as a predictor of stress management while engaging in flexible online learning during COVID-19. *International Journal Paper Public Review*, 2(2), 52-61. <https://doi.org/10.47667/ijppr.v2i2.89>
- Global Sports (2019, February 22). Global Sustainable Development through the power of Sport. Retrieved from <https://intelligence.globalsportsjobs.com/sport-a-powerful-tool-to-achieve-the-sustainable-development-goals>
- Graham, C. (2020, August 19). Are women happier than men? Do gender rights make a difference? Brookings. Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/are-women-happier-than-men-do-gender-rights-make-a-difference/>
- Gutierrez, A., Guzman, N. G., Ramos, R., & Uylengco, J. K. A. (2022). The Empirical Change of Playing Habits among Children. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(2), 303-317. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.02.15>
- Jackson S.B., Stevenson K.T., Larson L.R., Peterson M.N., & Seekamp E. (2021). Outdoor Activity Participation Improves Adolescents’ Mental Health and Well-Being during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18052506>
- Keskin, B., Güvendi, B., Karakoc, B., Kaya, S., & Cetin, O. (2022). The Relationship between the Digital Game Addiction Levels of Secondary and High School Students and Their Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity during the Pandemic Process. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.4 No.4. <https://doi.org/10.31014/aior.1993.04.04.373>
- Korpershoek, H., King, R. B., McInerney, D. M., Nasser, R. N., Ganotice, F. A., & Watkins, D. A. (2021). Gender and cultural differences in school motivation. *Research Papers in Education*, 36(1), 27–51. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2019.1633557>
- Lee, A.Y., Seon-Ok K., and Sin-Ae P. (2021). Attention and Emotional States during Horticultural Activities of Adults in 20s Using Electroencephalography: A Pilot Study. *Sustainability* .13(23), 12968. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132312968>
- Leong, D. C.P. (2022). Emotional Stability and Motivation of 21st Century Learners: A Comparative Review of Learning Theories. *Quantum Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3(6), 68–80. <https://doi.org/10.55197/qjssh.v3i6.190>
- Lobo J. A sudden shift: Students' perception of distance and online education in physical education amidst COVID-19 Pandemic. (2022). *Edu Sportivo: Indonesian Journal of Physical Education*, 200-216. [https://doi.org/10.25299/es:ijope.2022.vol3\(3\).9276](https://doi.org/10.25299/es:ijope.2022.vol3(3).9276)
- Mahfuzhoh, E., & Marcillia, S.R. (2024). Importance of children’s recess play exploration within school outdoor environment. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1301/1/012004>
- Martin, A., Chambers, S., Zucca, C., Chng, N.R., & Traynor, O. (2023). Outdoor nature-based play in early learning and childcare

centres: identifying the determinants of implementation using causal loop diagrams and social network analysis. *Health and Place*, 79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2022.102955>

McConatha, J.T. (2022). Loneliness, Isolation, and Internet Use Among Older Adults: How much Internet Use is Too much? Retrieved from *The Amplifier Magazine*. <https://div46amplifier.com/2022/12/14/loneliness-isolation-and-internet-use-among-older-adults-how-much-internet-use-is-too-much/>

Mungcal, K., Serrano, J.W., & Tolentino, J.C. (2021). Exploring Motives and Barriers to Exercise among “At-risk and Obese” Filipino College Students. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management and Sustainable Development*, 9, 100-109. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356666231_Exploring_Motives_and_Barriers_to_Exercise_among_At-risk_and_Obese_Filipino_College_Students

Nakshine, V. S., Thute, P., Khatib, M. N., & Sarkar, B. (2022). Increased Screen Time as a Cause of Declining Physical, Psychological Health, and Sleep Patterns: A Literary Review. *Cureus*, 14(10), e30051. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.30051>

Oga-Baldwin, W.L.Q. & Fryer, L.K. (2020). Girls show better quality motivation to learn languages than boys: latent profiles and their gender differences. *Heliyon*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04054>

Othman, Noratikah & Khairuz, Muhammad & Sumaiyah Jamaludin, Thandar Soe. (2020). The Impact of Electronic Gadget Uses with Academic Performance among Secondary School Students. *Prac Clin Invest* 2(2): 56-60. Retrieved from https://researchgate.net/publication/338791252_The_Impact_of_Electronic_Gadget_Uses_with_Academic_Performance_among_Secondary_School_Students

Paramita, P. E., Zulkifli, Z., Aziz, F., Supendi, D., & Muhammadiyah, M. (2023). Analysis of The Influence of Gadgets on Children's Emotional Intelligence. *Jurnal Scientia*, 12(01), 132-137. <https://doi.org/10.58471/scientia.v12i01.1057>

Peris-Ramos, H.C., Míguez, M.C., Rodriguez-Besteiro, S., David-Fernandez, S., Clemente-Suárez, V.J. (2024). Gender-Based Differences in Psychological, Nutritional, Physical Activity, and Oral Health Factors Associated with Stress in Teachers. *International Journal of Environmental Research Public Health*, 21, 385. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21040385>

Piores, V. F., Dev, R. D. O., Muhamad, M. M., & Kari, D. N. P. M. (2024). Gadget use and physical activity among children: Involvement Process Theory. *Journal of Physical Education*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4025/jphyseduc.v34i1.3456>

Przybylski, A. K., Nguyen, T. T., Law, W., & Weinstein, N. (2021). Does Taking a Short Break from Social Media Have a Positive Effect on Well-being? Evidence from Three Preregistered Field Experiments. *Journal of Technology in Behavioral Science*, 6(3), 507–514. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41347-020-00189-w>

Rasheed, A.R., Kamsin, A., & Abdullah, N.A. (2020). Challenges in the online component of blended learning: A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103701>

Robinson, J. (2020). A Parent’s Role in Outdoor Play Honours Bachelor of Early Childhood Leadership. Source, Honours Bachelor of Early Childhood Leadership (HBECL) Capstone Research Posters, 7. Retrieved from https://source.sheridancollege.ca/fahcs_student_capstones_hbecl/7/

Runner (2019). *The Journal of the Health and Physical Education Council of the Alberta Teachers’ Association* Volume 50, Number 1. Retrieved from Runner.

Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. Self-Determination Theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness. (2020). *Contemporary Educational Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1521/978.14625/28806>

Sergi, M.R., Picconi, L., Tommasi, M., Saggino, Aristide., Ebisch, S.J.H., & Spoto, A. (2021). The Role of Gender in the Association Among the Emotional Intelligence, Anxiety and Depression. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.747702>

Slavinski, T., Bjelica, D., Pavlović, D., & Vukmirović, V. (2021). Academic Performance and Physical Activities as Positive Factors for Life Satisfaction among University Students. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020497>

Šnele, M. S., Todorović, J., & Komlenić, M. (2020). Gender Roles and dimensions of family functioning as predictors of subjective well-being in men and women. *TEME*, 681-701. Retrieved from <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=911555>

Tkeshelashvili, M., Bolkvadze, M., Shaikh, A.P., Shaikh, N., Adhav, S., Glonti, S., & Nakashidze, I. (2023). A Study of digital addiction in Children during COVID-19 (Pandemic) conditions. *Translational and Clinical Medicine - Georgian Medical Journal*. 08. 34-38. Retrieved from <http://tcm.tsu.ge/index.php/TCM-GMJ/article/view/407>

Twenge, J. M. (2020). Why increases in adolescent depression may be linked to the technological environment. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 32, 89–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2019.06.036>

World Health Organization. (2022, October 5). Physical activity. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact->

sheets/detail/physical-activity

Wu, C., & Lu, L. (2023). Technology-based Physical Activities and Adults' physical activities levels, mental health, and Life satisfaction and Happiness: A Mixed Methods Study. *Research Square* (Research Square). <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3174482/v1>

Zhang W., Qiu L., Tang F., & Sun H.J. (2023). Gender differences in cognitive and affective interpersonal emotion regulation in couples: an fNIRS hyperscanning. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, Volume 18, Issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scan/nsad057>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Vanessa Mae J. Lagmay

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Jaemari Anne M. Padilla

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Chloe Therese T. De Los Santos

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Kevin Brian DC. Inocentes

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Arianne Rose V. Casinto

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines

Selica Misty N. Navarrete

St. Dominic College of Asia – Philippines